

Gender Inequality and Its Causes & Types

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Abstract

Indian system is very complex because its social, religious and cultural practices and its other issues like education, employment, opportunities, these issues effect can be seen on the life women because it makes a difference between men and women. Women are traditionally considered by society as weaker gender. She has been accorded a subordinate position to men. women still live in present day, in the same condition of the past. Women have no power to take decisions independently either inside their home or out side the work. Lack of education is the main cause of it in present time. The unfortunate part of gender inequality in our society, is that women face social customs, beliefs and patriarchal system.

Key words: Gender, Inequality, Gender Inequality Causes & Types.

Gender inequality means disparity between men and women in differential social, economical, political, cultural and legal aspects. This study considers the gender inequality that exist among the Indian system on the bases of its causes. Indian system is very complex because its social, religious and cultural practices and its other issues like education, employment, opportunities, these issues effect can be seen on the life women because it makes a difference between men and women. Traditional patriarchy customs and norms have relegated women to secondary status with in the house-hold and work place. An attempt has been made to find out those causes which are responsible for this problem in India.

Gender inequality may be defined as discrimination against women based on their sex. Women are traditionally considered by society as weaker gender. She has been accorded a subordinate position to men. She is exploited, degraded, violated and discriminated both in our homes and in outside the world. Traditional value system, low level of literary, more house hold responsibilities, lack of awareness, non-availability of proper guidance, low mobility, lack of self confidence, family discouragement and advanced science and technology are some of factors responsible to create gender disparity in our society.¹ According to Amartya Sen (2001) there are seven types of gender inequalities in India. Here is brief explanation of all the types of gender inequality.

1. Concept of Gender Inequality :

Gender is a socio-cultural created concept which attribute different social roles and identities to men and women. The initial move was to use the term sex is referd to the biological difference between men and women, while gender indicate the vast range of cultural meaning attached to the basic difference. Sex makes us male or female; gender makes us masculine or feminine.

When we talk about inequality among men and women, it means various things, human beings are inequality placed that they have unequal opportunities. Gender inequality is defined as discrimination against women based on their sex. She exploited, violated and discriminated both

in our homes and outside the world. Gender inequality in India refers to education, economic and political inequalities between men and women.

2. Morality Inequality :

Inequality between men and women directly involves matters of life and death and take the brutal form of unusually high mortality rates for women and consequent preponderance of men in the total population as opposed to the preponderance of women found in societies with little or no gender bias in health care and nutrition.

3. Natality Inequality :

Given the preference for boys over girls that characterized many male dominated societies, gender inequality can manifest itself in the form of parents' wanting a baby to be boy rather than a girl.

4. Basic Facility Inequality :

Even when demographic characteristics do not show much anti-female bias or any at all, there are other ways in which women can get less than a square deal. There are many countries in Asia where girls have a far less opportunity for schooling than do boys.

5. Special-Opportunity Inequality :

Even when there is relatively little difference in basic facilities including schooling, the opportunities for higher education may be far fewer for young women than for young men. Indeed gender bias in higher education and professional training can be observed in the many countries of the world.

6. Socialization :

Socialization is the process through which child becomes an individual respecting his or her environment law norms and customs. It is teach how children of different sexes are socialized into their gender role and taught what it means to be male or female. Through contract the primary and secondary agencies of socialization, children gradually internalize with the norms of society 'Gender differences are not biologically determined, they are culturally produced, gender inequalities result because men and women are socialized into different roles. Socialization arise most important question in our mind is it a boy or a girl and according to this new it is in comes including under the causes of gender inequality in Indian system / society.

7. Professional Inequality :

In employment as well as promotion in work and occupation, women often face greater handicaps than man.

8. Patriarchal System:

The main roots of disparity in Indian society is that it lies in the patriarchal system. Patriarchy is a system of social structure and practices in which men dominate, oppress and exploit women. Women's exploitation is an old age cultural phenomenon of Indian society. Patriarchy means the manifestation and institution alization of male dominance over women and children in the family and the extension of male dominance over women in society. Male domination over women's ideology comes through the patriarchy.

9. Household Inequality :

Often there are fundamental inequalities in gender relations with in the family or the household. This can take many different forms. Even in cases in which there are no overt sign of anti bias in say mortality rates, or male domination, male preference in birth, education, family arrangement can be quite unequal in terms of sharing the Burdon of housework and child care.

10. Ownership Inequality :

In many societies, the ownership of property can also be very unequal. Even basic assets such as homes and land may be very asymmetrically shared. The absence of claims to property can not only reduce the voice of women, it can also make it harder for women to enter to flourish in commercial, economic and even in social activities. These are main type of gender inequality that is faced by the female in the society.

The most important causes of gender inequality such as :

- (i) **Poverty** : In India of the total 30 percent people who are below poverty line, 70 percent are women². Women's poverty in India is directly related to the absence of economic opportunities and lack of access to economic resources including credit, land ownership and inheritance and their minimal participation in decision making process.
- (ii) **Illiteracy** : The female literacy rate in India is lower than the male literacy rate. According to census of India 2011, literacy rate of 65.46 percent compared males which are 82.14 percent³. Though it is gradually rising, the female literacy rate in India is lower than the male literacy rate. Compared to boys, for fewer girls are enrolled in the schools and many of them dropout.
- (iii) **Lack of Employment Facilities** : Some common inequalities that take place in the workplace are the gender based imbalances of individuals in power and command over the management of the organizations. In addition child bearing and rearing of children has clear implications for labour force participations by women.
- (iv) **Social Customs, Beliefs and Practices** : Women are not free from social customs, beliefs and practices. The traditional patrilineal joint family system confines women's roles mostly to the domestic sphere allocating them to a subordinate status, authority and power compared to men. The preference for sons and disfavor towards daughter is complex phenomenon that still persists in many places³. Sons are often only the person related through one's male kin⁴. Boys are given the inclusive rights to inherit the family name and properties and they are viewed as additional status of their family.
- (v) **Social Attitudes** : Most of India has strong patriarchal custom, where men hold authority over female family members and inherit property and title. It is a custom where father inheritance passes from father to son, women move in with husband and his family upon marriage and marriages include a bride price or dowry⁵. The social stigma that women are housekeepers and should be confined to the four walls of the house is perhaps a viable cause of gender disparity.
- (vi) **Lack of Awareness of Women** : Most of the women are unaware of their basic rights and capabilities. They even do not have the understanding as to how the socio-economic and political forces affect them. If women get equal opportunities like men, they can work in every field like men⁶. But women faced this situation many centuries and the main fault of our traditions behind them.

On the basis of above discussion we can interpret there are many causes of gender disparity in India. India needs to deactivate the gender inequality. It is surprising that in spite so many laws of Indian constitution. Women domination and faced many discrimination in family and society.

Legislative System :

Indian constitution provides positive efforts to eliminate gender inequality; the preamble to the constitution talks about goals of achieving social, economic and political justice to everyone and to provide equality of status and opportunity to all its citizens. Article (14), 15(3), 15(1) also laid down the state make special provision for equality of women. The fundamental rights of Indian constitution are guaranteed, but also have not to be able to ensure equality for women in all sphere.

In India, people make joke of constitution and justice system. Rape and others crimes is the live example of it. Men are made to believe their very infancy that it is in their power and boundary to misuse a girl and women publicity and otherwise the way they want. This feeling is so deep rooted in

our Indian men psyche. A Total of 327394 cases of crimes against women were reported in the country during the year 2015. The crime continuously increasing and so many cases in which victims are walk freely and they courage others.

Conclusion:

On the basis of above discussion about the causes of gender inequality, we can see that women still live in present day, in the same condition of the past. Women have no power to take decisions independently either inside their home or out side the work. Lack of education is the main cause of it in present time. The unfortunate part of gender inequality in our society, is that women face social customs, beliefs and patriarchal system.

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